

MULTI-SCALE DAMAGE MODELING IN ABAQUS

H. de Boer*, J.J.M. Koppert*, A. Beukers**, H.E.N. Bersee**

*Advanced Lightweight Engineering, ** Delft University of Technology
Rotterdamseweg 145, 2628AL Delft, The Netherlands
deboer@ale.nl

SUMMARY

A multi-scale damage model for composite materials has been developed. It is based on properties of constituents and applies homogenization methods. The multi-scale damage model, together with a graphical user interface, is implemented in the commercial software package ABAQUS. The accuracy and efficiency of the present model will be evaluated by means of an industrial example.

Keywords: Multi-scale, Damage model, ABAQUS, Homogenization, Composites

INTRODUCTION

In modern aircraft fuselage design advanced composite materials are increasingly utilised. Over the years Advanced Lightweight Engineering (ALE) has accumulated unique expertise in numerical damage modeling of composites and hybrid materials. These models have been developed in ABAQUS and include delamination, fiber/matrix failure, fracture energies, temperature effects, etc. This paper deals with a multi-scale progressive damage model for composite materials.

MULTI-SCALE DAMAGE MODEL

Model description and GUI

Traditionally, composite properties obtained by testing are used directly in the FE models. In the present paper it is suggested to calculate the composite properties based on the properties of the constituents, i.e. fiber and matrix. The present approach is based on a homogenization scheme like Mori-Tanaka. Such a homogenization scheme is purely analytical and therefore computationally inexpensive. Both stiffness and strength are predicted by the model. It has several modeling advantages over the traditional method, since e.g. voids and fiber misalignments can easily be included. In addition, this method has advantages related to damage modeling. Stress and strain in the constituent phases can be calculated based on composite stress and strain. Herewith, significantly more accurate failure criteria can be implemented. Furthermore, the homogenization scheme enables a consistent method to reduce composite properties after failure initiation by simply reducing the properties of the constituents.

The present multi-scale method utilizes Eshelby tensors and modified Mori-Tanaka [1] homogenization scheme, combined with Classical Laminate Theory. More details on the formulation will follow in the full paper. Main focus during the development of the

model was on accurate and efficient simulation of failure predictions and residual strength. Very promising results have been obtained using simple shell elements.

The multi-scale model has been implemented in Abaqus using the user subroutines UMAT, VUMAT and USDFLD. Furthermore, a Graphical User Interface for Abaqus/CAE has been implemented as well, see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Graphical User Interface for Abaqus/CAE

Example

The example presented here deals with a three stringer stiffened CFRP panel, see Figure 2. In the centre of the middle stringer an initial delamination is included. The panel is loaded in compression. Before actually testing the panel, the new multi-scale damage model has been used to predict the final failure load and failure mode. Both failure mode and failure load were accurately predicted by the model (5% difference compared to average test data, conservative). Using standard Abaqus failure models led to a 40% overprediction of the strength of the panel.

Figure 2 Failure of artificially damaged stringer stiffened panel

Conclusions

The present multi-scale damage model is capable to accurately predict both failure initiation and final failure of composite structures. The implementation in the commercial software Abaqus combined with a dedicated GUI ensures ease of use.

References

1. Mori T., Tanaka K.: Average Stress in the Matrix and Average Elastic Energy of Materials with Misfitting Inclusions; Acta metall. 21, 571-574, 1973.